

Manual B

Supply list for Tissue Culture Procedure

Review to make sure you have all supplies at the worktable

1. Face masks prevent breathing contaminants onto cultures.
2. Sterilant (Bleach and water) to sterilize work surfaces.
3. Saucepan to mix and heat tissue culture media reagents.
4. Table sugar for tissue culture media
5. All-purpose water-soluble fertilizer 10-10-10
6. Inositol Powder for culture media
7. Vitamin tablet with thiamine for culture media
8. Pill cutter/crusher to cut vitamin tablet
9. Long handle spoon to stir boiling medium
10. Agar Flakes for culture media
11. Measuring cups for culture media
12. Measuring spoons for culture media
13. Potholders for handling hot jars and tools
14. Long handle tongs for removing jars and tools from pressure cooker
15. Kitchen towels to clean up water drops
16. Pressure-safe glass container with lids (baby food jars; mason jars; etc.) to withstand repeated sterilization in the pressure cooker.
17. Pressure cooker to sterilize materials and tools.
18. Muslin cloth is used to wrap sterile objects to prevent contamination before use.
19. Scissors to take a stem cutting
20. Dish soap to clean glassware and tools and act as a surfactant aiding in removal of contaminants.
21. Sterile long-handled tweezers to manipulate plant tissues.
22. Sterile cutting implement (razor blade) to cut plant tissues.
23. 70% Rubbing alcohol disinfects surfaces and skin.
24. Distilled water as a high purity water source to prevent contamination and to rinse plant tissue
25. Plastic wrap to cover container openings to prevent contamination
26. Paper towels wrapped in aluminum foil and sterilized to provide a sterile surface for tissue manipulation
27. Spray bottle with sterilant to clean surfaces
28. Nitrile gloves to prevent transmission of contaminants
29. Appropriate plant to propagate (coleus, begonias, African violet)
30. Culture medium (supplies and recipe below)

Maintaining Sterility

Supplies needed to help create and maintain a sterile environment

- Plastic wrap to cover containers
- Cloth towels
- Paper towels
- Spray bottle with 70% rubbing alcohol
- Nitrile gloves
- Face masks
- Sterilant (Water with Bleach) in spray bottle
- Muslin cloth
- Dish soap

Follow these steps to sterilize the work area. Keep the work area clutter-free while performing culturing. Before placing jars, measuring cups, or cutting tools on the work surface, spray with sterilant solution. Open containers only when ready to use. Keep items wrapped otherwise.

Creating Tissue Culture Medium

Supplies needed to mix and sterilize medium

- Sterilant (Water with bleach)
- Saucepan
- Pressure-safe glass container with lids (baby food jars; mason jars; etc.)
- Pressure cooker
- Aluminum foil
- Dish soap
- Distilled water
- 70% Rubbing alcohol

Recipe: 1 pint Tissue Culture Medium

- Table sugar (1/8 cup)
- Distilled water (1 cup)
- All-purpose water-soluble fertilizer 10-10-10 (1 cup stock solution)
- Inositol powder (1/8 tsp)
- Vitamin tablet with thiamine (1/4 tablet, crushed)
- Agar flakes (2 tablespoons) or Gelatin (3 tablespoons)

Making Culture Medium

Clean your hands and work areas with 70% rubbing alcohol. Put on gloves. Wash the pressure-safe glassware with a 10% bleach solution. (spray with solution in spray bottle). Follow fertilizer label instructions to mix 10-10-10 fertilizer stock solution. Pour 1 cup of stock into the saucepan. (fertilizer stock is pre-mixed). Quarter a thiamine tablet; crush one piece. Save the rest. Add the crushed tablet to the saucepan. Add 1/8 tsp inositol powder to the saucepan. Add 1/8 cup of table sugar, 1 cup of distilled water, and 2 tablespoons of agar flakes into the saucepan. Mix all ingredients together in a saucepan.

Boil, at medium-high heat (7-8) stirring constantly, until agar dissolves (2-5 mins). Pour the mixture into pressure-safe jars to a depth of at least 1 inch (the 2oz. mark on the jar). Sterilize the jars with loosely screwed-on lids (or put lids on up-side down) in hot water bath. Pressure cook at 15 psi (HI for electric cookers) for 15 minutes to sterilize. Remove hot items with a tongs. Tighten the lids on the jars and place them in the refrigerator once cooled.

Establishment of Aseptic Culture

Supplies needed prepare plant for culture

- Selected plant
- Sterile Scissors
- Sterile long-handled tweezers
- Sterilant (water with bleach)
- Dish soap
- Distilled water
- Culture medium
- 70% Rubbing alcohol

Culture Initiation

Disinfect scissors with 10% bleach. Clean your hands and work areas with 70% rubbing alcohol. Put on gloves. Wrap tweezers and scissors (or razor blade) in clean, dry cotton cloth (muslin or towel).

Pressure cook tools at 15 psi for 15 minutes to sterilize. Remove hot items with tongs. Allow them to cool while you sterilize the plant material. Cut a 2-3 node stem cutting. Disinfect scissors between cuttings with 10% bleach. Process promptly for optimal results. If necessary,

Keep explants cold until use.

Mix 3–5 drops of dish soap into a container of 10% bleach solution; it should be large enough to submerge the cuttings. Add the plant pieces and swirl container.(for this workshop for 3 minutes). Slide top of lid to side leaving small gap at rim, drain the water, avoid spilling the plant cuttings.

Refill the container with distilled water and swirl to rinse. Repeat steps 7 to 9 four times. If needed, lay out a sterile paper towel and trim off the bleach-burnt tissue. With lid on, clean the exterior of your culture medium containers with 10% bleach before using. Open jar, placing lids face down. (if using multiple jars open one at a time). Gently grasp the cutting with your tweezers. Sanitize tweezers between cuttings with 10% bleach. Embed at least one node of the cutting into the medium.

Label lid with date, and store jars in the selected culture room. A 75°F room with 16 hours of light is ideal. Inspect cultures every 3-5 days; discard contaminated or dead cultures. Clean the jar with a 10% bleach solution before reusing.